

Level of nationalism and level of heritage conservation of pre-service teachers

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ABSTRACT

The study was an attempt to determine the respondent's perception on level of nationalism in terms of preservation, restoration, heritage built, safeguarding historical places, and property value. Using a descriptive-correlation method of research, it involved 200 pre-service teachers from Southern Luzon State University - Lucban during the academic year 2021-2022. The adapted-modified questionnaire was utilized to gather the needed data. The results of the test of the relationship between nationalism and heritage conservation among pre-service teachers indicate that there is a significant positive relationship between the respondents' levels of nationalism and level of heritage conservation. This suggests that as students' nationalism grows, also their awareness to heritage conservation increases. This research suggests that the College of Teacher Education may provide opportunities among the pre-service teachers to strengthen their nationalism and participation in heritage conservation as part of the curriculum contents of the subject in Social Sciences. Pre-service teachers may be encouraged to inculcate the value of heritage in their students through learning activities in face-to-face, blended learning, modular distance learning, or online media platforms in their teaching of the subject in social science. Pre-service teachers may be encouraged to participate on different activities related to heritage conservation that encourage positive relationships and nationalism. Future researchers may utilize this research work as basis in conducting similar studies.

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INTRODUCTION

Another justification for making strong efforts to preserve heritage is nationalism. Here, historical locations, occasions, and artifacts serve as a metaphor for what is admirable about a country or its people (Timothy, 2017). Few studies have made belonging itself the subject of inquiry, despite the fact that existing research in the fields of national identity, the nation, and, in particular, nationalism, has examined the significance of belonging for nations and nationalism scholarship (Knott, 2017). All six members of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) have made considerable investments in the growth of their regional heritage industries during the past ten years. These nations have increased their initiatives to promote domestic nationalism concurrently. Studies on the growth of the heritage sector typically go under the anthropological, sociological, or museum studies categories, but those on nationalism are more likely to fall under the political science category.

Winter (2012) looks at the connections between nationalism and cultural heritage. Both contemporary examples and a historical explanation of these linkages are provided. A lot of focus is placed on the part that antiquity has played and is still playing in the development of cultural nationalisms, some of which have not been very good. He contends that the connections between nationalism and nation-making movements that evolved around the world starting in the late nineteenth century and archaeology and architectural conservation are still strong today. The "classical age" architecture of antiquity continues to be a major focal point for international cultural nationalism.

In the Philippines, nationalism is inherently in conflict with the possibility of an egalitarian, postcolonial existence on the one hand, and dynastic/colonial modes of perception on the other. However, the methods used to imagine nationhood may occasionally be at odds with the very nature of the images that are reproduced (Teehanke, 2016). Goode and Stroup (2015) claimed that everyday nationalism holds promise for bridging the methodological individualism of earlier studies with constructivist theory. This method builds on ethnographic observation and relies on techniques for verification that depend on monitoring social interaction or relational meaning formation. We use the nationalist legitimization of authoritarian regimes and the ethnicization of economic development as examples to exemplify such a study technique.

The qualities of teacher training that enhance pre-service teachers' capacity to instruct a diverse student body were studied and examined by Akiba (2012). The association between preparatory factors and pre-service teachers' multicultural awareness, knowledge, and abilities has, however, only been the subject of a small number of empirical investigations. Without taking into account the factors influencing teacher preparation, the majority of quantitative research merely evaluated a proposed shift in pre-service teachers' intercultural attitudes, awareness, and beliefs over the course of one course. Coordinators of teacher education programs and teacher educators have a key role in educating pre-service teachers to acquire multicultural awareness, knowledge, and abilities for teaching different pupils (Akiba, 2012). With this in mind, the researchers are interested in disseminating information about nationalism and heritage conservation. He also intends to focus his study on nationalism of the respondents and how it contributes in enhancing the level of awareness on heritage conservation of pre-service teachers.

OBJECTIVES

In this study generally, the researchers were interested in disseminating information about nationalism and heritage conservation. He also intends to focus his study on nationalism of the respondents and how it contributes in enhancing the level of awareness on heritage conservation of pre-service teachers.

METHODS

Design

A descriptive correlational study is a study in which the researchers is primarily interested in describing relationships among variables, without seeking to establish a causal connection. This study employed the

descriptive- correlational research as a short-circuit route to surface the truth of the meaningful aspects. The study utilized a self-made survey questionnaire that answered the research questions of the undertaking.

Respondents and sampling technique

The respondents of the researchers were selected pre-service teachers at Southern Luzon State University – Lucban Campus and were chosen through random sampling. Concerning nationalism and its relationship to heritage conservation of pre-service teacher’s instrument was developed and utilized: questionnaires to measure levels of nationalism and heritage conservation for the validation of the questionnaire, the questionnaires were administered to the pool of experts comprising of selected teachers in public school. Whereas, rephrasing of some of the questions in layman’s term is suggested. The results were incorporated in the final copy of the questionnaire’s reproduction. Before doing actual research, the result was computed to determine the validity of the questionnaire with a Cronbach Alpha level of 0.976 (Excellent).

Ethical considerations and data collections

After ensuring the permission of the dean of the college, the researchers have posted a call for participants in this research via Facebook and Instagram. Those pre-service teachers who positively showed interest to be the respondents of this study joined a meeting through Google Meet to discuss the scope and their role in this undertaking. When the consent was given by the respondents, the researchers administered the self-made questionnaire via Google form. After answering all the questions, the results were tallied.

Data analysis

After the final draft of the questionnaires was final, it was reproduced and administered by the researchers. The first part of the study is the respondents’ level of nationalism and level of heritage conservation. The second part of the study is the respondents’ summary of perceived level of nationalism and level of heritage conservation. To be able to interpret the computed weighted mean, the following mean ranges with their corresponding interpretations will be used. The following statistical measures were employed to determine the nationalism and heritage conservation of the respondents: Mean. This was used to interpret the nationalism and heritage conservation of the respondents. Standard Deviation. This was used to determine the variability of the involvement in types of heritage conservation in terms of levels of nationalism in the researchers adapted-modified questionnaire. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This was used to determine if there is significant difference exists in the respondents’ heritage conservation when grouped according to their nationalism.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Part 1. Profile of the respondents

Table 1. Respondents’ Profile According to Majorship

Major	Frequency	Percent
English	37	18.4%
Filipino	38	18.9%
General Education	12	6.5%
MAPEH	9	4.5%
Mathematics	28	13.9%
Science	31	15.4%
Social Studies	44	21.9%
TLE	1	0.5%
Over-all	200	100.00

The table shows that out of 200 respondents, 37 students or 18.4 percent are English majors, 38 students or 18.90 percent are Filipino majors, 12 students or 6.50 percent are General Education majors, 9 students or 4.50 percent are MAPEH majors, 28 students or 13.90 percent are Mathematics majors, 31 students or 15.40 percent are Science majors, 44 students or 21.90 percent are Social Studies majors, while 1 student or 0.50 percent, is TLE major.

Part II: Practices on Types of Nationalism

Table 2 Respondents' Level of Preservation

<i>I ...</i>	Mean	SD	VI
1. provide regular upkeep for historic area	3.38	.55	Agree
2. ensure that all preservation methods are to keep historic property or landmark	3.42	.55	Agree
3. create a local historic preservation campaign that gives residents the authority they need to protect their identity	3.34	.65	Agree
4. am aware of current penalties for violating historic preservation acts and laws	3.35	.66	Agree
5. make historic preservation diverse and increase engagement with the community	3.46	.60	Agree
Overall	3.39	.48	Agree

Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Table 2 presents the respondents' perception on level of nationalism in terms of preservation which reveals that the respondents agreed that making historic preservation diverse and increase engagement with the community with a mean 3.46 which garnered the highest mean. Oppositely, the respondents also agreed that creating a local historic preservation campaign that gives residents the authority they need to protect their identity which obtained a mean of 3.34. and over-all mean of 3.39.

Table 3 Respondents' Level of Restoration

<i>I...</i>	Mean	SD	VI
1. 1. explore and implement best practices connecting historic preservation and restoration.	3.46	.57	Agree
2. am aware to programs to preserve and enhance heritage properties.	3.34	.61	Agree
3. support community efforts for appropriate information on restoration.	3.57	.58	Agree
4. advocate for maintaining and expanding historical ideas on restoration to provide knowledge.	3.49	.62	Agree
5. work with the others to ensure that restored heritage is well-maintained and protected.	3.45	.63	Agree
Overall	3.46	.49	Agree

Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Shown in Table 3 is the respondents' level of nationalism in terms of restoration. The statement, supporting community efforts for appropriate information on restoration got the highest mean of 3.57. However, awareness to programs to preserve and enhance heritage properties garnered the lowest mean of 3.34.

Table 4 *Respondents' Level of Heritage built*

<i>I...</i>	Mean	SD	VI
1. appreciate tangible heritage such as movable, immovable and heritage sites.	3.59	.54	Strongly Agree
2. value the importance of heritage.	3.73	.48	Strongly Agree
3. aware on historical sites in the Philippines.	3.45	.56	Agree
4. involve in the promotion of heritage in the community.	3.39	.62	Agree
5. develop steps on the protection of history and heritage.	3.41	.63	Agree
Overall	3.51	.45	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

The table illustrates the respondents' level of nationalism in terms of heritage built. Valuing the importance of heritage obtained the highest mean of 3.73. Meanwhile, involving in the promotion of heritage in the community garnered the lowest mean of 3.39.

Table 5 *Respondents' Level of Safeguarding historical places*

<i>I...</i>	Mean	SD	VI
1. responsible for ensuring the permanent coordination to the community.	3.45	.57	Agree
2. safeguarding plans and documents should be drawn up, once all the necessary advance scientific studies have been carried out, by multidisciplinary teams involved in the protection and enhancement of historic areas.	3.44	.58	Agree
3. lead in sounding the opinions and organizing the participation of the public concerned.	3.39	.62	Agree
4. develop safeguarding plans and documents should be approved by the body designated by law.	3.43	.64	Agree
5. responsible for giving effect to the safeguarding provisions and regulations at all levels, national, regional and local, should be provided with the necessary staff and given adequate technical, administrative and financial resources.	3.42	.60	Agree
Overall	3.43	.53	Agree

Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Table 5 describes the respondents' level of nationalism in terms of safeguarding historical places. The statement which describes that the respondents' responsibility for ensuring the permanent coordination to the community garnered the highest mean of 3.45. Meanwhile, leading in sounding the opinions and organizing the participation of the public concerned got the lowest mean of 3.39.

Table 6 *Respondents' Level of Property value*

<i>I...</i>	Mean	SD	VI
1. proud of my identity and nationality.	3.82	.42	Strongly Agree
2. understand the culture and aesthetic relationship.	3.74	.45	Strongly Agree
3. show patriotism towards built heritage, historical landmarks, etc.	3.72	.48	Strongly Agree
4. am aware on property value of heritage sites and historical markers.	3.60	.53	Strongly Agree
5. raising awareness and equality to create inclusive society pertaining to heritage.	3.66	.53	Strongly Agree

Overall	3.71	.40	Strongly Agree
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Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

The table shows the respondents’ level of nationalism in terms of property value. The respondents strongly agreed that they are proud of their identity and nationality with the highest mean of 3.82. While awareness on property value of heritage sites and historical markers got the lowest mean of 3.60.

Table 7 Summary of Perceived Level of Nationalism

Types	Mean	SD	VI
Preservation	3.39	.48	High
Restoration	3.46	.49	High
Heritage built	3.51	.45	Very High
Safeguarding historical places	3.43	.53	High
Property value	3.71	.40	Very High
Overall Level of Nationalism	3.50	.41	Very High

Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

The summary of level of nationalism is presented in this table. Property value got the highest mean of 3.71. On the other hand, preservation garnered the lowest mean of 3.39. Based on the results, the respondents were agreeing in preserving heritage. Preservation plays a vital role in heritage conservation because it increases the process of valuing important part of our rich culture and history. Through preservation it also gives strong sense of connection to the past. Recognizing the importance of our interest in this process gives legacy to our own identity.

Heritage markers not only inform the public about heritage structures’ importance to Filipino history and culture. They also work to shield these historic structures from destruction. This ensures that their appearance is closest to how they appeared centuries ago (Tantuico, 2020).

Thus, this means that the respondents are willing to support heritage conservation through restoration. Most of the examples of restoration focuses on maintaining historical sites and buildings. Lack of awareness to other programs is because of insufficient knowledge on the wider view of heritage. However, through the collaborative efforts it gives value to protect and maintain cultural belongingness.

Part III. Level of Heritage Conservation

Table 8 Respondents’ Level of Heritage Conservation in terms of Community Participation

I...	Mean	SD	VI
1. recognize that heritage encourages a variety of cultural activities from the local population	3.54	.53	Strongly Agree
2. know that local people should be consulted when tourism and heritage conservation policies are being made	3.53	.57	Strongly Agree
3. understand the benefits of tourism and heritage in the community	3.61	.57	Strongly Agree
4. want to promote community-based tourism initiatives and heritage conservation activities	3.56	.54	Strongly Agree
5. am willing to attend the local government programs on heritage conservation to increase awareness	3.56	.54	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.56	.45	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Table 8 presents community participation which depicts that the respondents understand the benefits of tourism and heritage in the community obtaining highest mean of 3.61. Among all indicators, statement that pertains to the respondents knowing that local people should be consulted when tourism and heritage conservation policies are being made got the lowest mean of 3.53. The overall mean is 3.56 with the verbal interpretation of “Strongly Agree.” Hence, it can be stated that involvement of the people in the community is beneficial in heritage conservation and tourism.

Through community participation it can boost the level of cooperation of the locals to help and promote their own heritage. stated that findings showed that motivation had the greatest positive effect on the low level of community participation. Opportunity had the greatest effect on the high level of community participation. Among the dimensions of ability, namely awareness and knowledge, the findings showed that more aware residents were more interested in low level of community participation, whereas residents with more knowledge were more interested in high level of community participation (Rasoolimanesh et. al, 2016).

Table 9 Respondents’ Level of Heritage Conservation in terms of Tourism Development

I...	Mean	SD	VI
1. understand the concept of sustainable tourism.	3.51	.58	Strongly Agree
2. promote tourism and encourage the community to participate.	3.50	.58	Strongly Agree
3. can see that the people in the community protect local heritage and tourism	3.47	.57	Agree
4. believe that well-managed attractions such as your maintained in their natural state, are important to attract tourism	3.59	.54	Strongly Agree
5. benefit from developing a sustainable tourism framework.	3.45	.59	Agree
Overall	3.51	.45	Strongly Agree

Legend:4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Shown in Table 9 is the respondents’ level of heritage conservation in terms of tourism development. The statement, believing that well-managed attractions such as your maintained in their natural state, are important to attract tourism got the highest mean of 3.59. However, benefit from developing a sustainable tourism framework garnered the lowest mean of 3.45.

This stated that heritage can be part of tourism attractions if it is well-preserved by the locals and supported by the government. Promoting tourism through heritage will also help the locals to provide an economic growth and sustainable tourism.

Given that community willingness to participate should not be taken for granted, it is proposed that the management of heritage through community-based research could form a paradigm of practice towards a more community-inclusive heritage tourism planning. This paradigm positions communities and their aspirations at the heart of its enquiry, emphasizing questions that revolve around the public understandings of heritage, the identification of community needs, and the accommodation of these needs through community involvement (Stephens & Tiwari, 2015).

Table 10 Respondents’ Level of Values on Heritage Conservation in terms of Historical Values

I...	Mean	SD	VI
1. am aware of significant events or historic phases	3.45	.56	Agree
2. maintain or show the continuity of a historical process or activity	3.48	.56	Agree
3. know some person/s whose life, career, or acts hold strong historical significance	3.47	.59	Agree
4. contribute to a sense of historical identity for a community	3.39	.59	Agree
5. identify that local memory is affected by street pattern and built form of the town	3.41	.56	Agree
Overall	3.44	.47	Agree

Legend:4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

This table depicts respondents' level of values on heritage conservation in terms of historical. Maintain or show the continuity of a historical process or activity got the highest mean of 3.47. Meanwhile, contributing to a sense of historical identity for a community got the lowest mean of 3.39.

This stated that the respondents involving themselves in the historical process will contribute impact to maintain the significance of history. Keeping the historical activities shows continuity of the historical process.

Avrami, 2017 reveals that conserving a historic property according to historical-cultural values would lead one to maximize the capacity for the place to serve the educational function of telling the stories; the primary audiences in this case might be local schoolchildren and the local community, for whom association with this old place and its stories makes a significant contribution to their group identity.

Table 11 Respondents' Level of Values on Heritage Conservation in terms of Aesthetic Values

<i>I...</i>	Mean	SD	VI
1. know important information for distinctive aesthetic attributes	3.44	.615	Agree
2. value the importance of creativity in creating design or technical advancement	3.55	.546	Strongly Agree
3. recognize landmark quality	3.42	.595	Agree
4. inculcate the importance for contribution to streetscape character	3.39	.607	Agree
5. ensure that aesthetic value can inspire and develop artistic awareness	3.44	.598	Agree
Overall	3.4460	.49468	Agree

Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

The table shows the respondents' level of values on heritage conservation in terms of aesthetic. The statement which describes that valuing the importance of creativity in creating design or technical advancement got the highest mean of 3.55. On the other hand, inculcate the importance for contribution to streetscape character garnered the lowest mean of 3.39.

This implies that aesthetic value increases the significance of beauty and uniqueness of heritage. Using the technical advancement, it creates more aesthetic and intrinsic designs. Through aesthetic value it also creates the harmonious relationship and appreciation of artistic awareness in the community.

Aesthetic significance due to its overall unity of the design of the theatre, or contributes to its aesthetic integrity, or intrinsic aesthetic qualities valued by the community. The extent to which a building demonstrates design and/or construction techniques or knowledge of the time; or whether the building has aesthetic significance due either to its uniqueness, or its being representative of commonly held ideas of beauty, design, and form; or whether the building or site has clear association with events or persons in history. (Minle, 2012)

Table 12 Respondents' Level of Values on Heritage Conservation in terms of Scientific Values

<i>I...</i>	Mean	SD	VI
1. apply research-based information on the promotion of heritage.	3.37	.63	Agree
2. advocate in depth understanding and scientific studies for the preservation of historic properties	3.41	.62	Agree
3. support scientific research for the development of heritage conservation	3.44	.60	Agree
4. am aware that heritage can inspire and develop knowledge	3.53	.58	Strongly Agree
5. work with organizations to ensure historic buildings are protected and restored	3.35	.67	Agree
Overall	3.42	.53	Agree
Overall Values	3.43	.46	Agree

Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Presented in Table 12 respondents' level of values on heritage conservation in terms of scientific. Attaining the highest mean of 3.53 the respondents strongly agreed that awareness on heritage can inspire and develop knowledge. Meanwhile, with the lowest mean of 3.35, working with organizations to ensure historic buildings are protected and restored.

This result signifies that we can create and stimulate learning about heritage through information and dissemination to increase awareness. Scientific research also supports the development heritage conservation in terms of scientific value. The overall values mean is 3.43 which are verbally interpreted as agree. Research into scientific heritage can be done from multiple areas of study, but the most important is the history of science, through material culture methodologies (Wilson, 2013).

Table 13: Summary of Perceived Level of Heritage Conservation

Types	Mean	SD	VI
Community Participation	3.56	.45	Very High
Tourism Development	3.51	.45	Very High
Historical Values	3.44	.47	High
Aesthetic Values	3.45	.49	High
Scientific Values	3.42	.53	High
Overall Values	3.43	.46	High
Overall Level of Values on Heritage Conservation	3.50	.41	Very High

Legend: 4.0-3.50 Strongly Agree/ Very High. 3.49-2.50 Agree/ High 2.49-1.50 Disagree/ Low. 1.49-1.0 Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Table 13 presents the summary of perceived level of heritage conservation. As can be seen, community participation got the highest mean of 3.56. On the other hand, scientific garnered the lowest mean of 3.42. The findings affirm that actively involvement on heritage by the locals in the community developed high level skills in heritage conservation process. However, scientific value is difficult to recognize by the citizens in every locality because of its technicality. Heritage values play a significant role. However, their effects do not always favor participation as they can also act as barriers to involvement. On the other hand, tourism perceptions are found to be mainly insignificant in shaping intentions to participate. (Dragouni, 2017)

Table 14. Correlation between respondents' level of nationalism and their heritage conservation

Practices of Nationalism	Level of Heritage Conservation						Level Heritage Conservation
	Community Participation	Tourism Development	Historical Values	Aesthetic Values	Scientific Values	Overall Values	
Preservation	.596**	.629**	.611**	.632**	.620**	.676**	.686**
Restoration	.654**	.673**	.702**	.683**	.707**	.759**	.754**
Heritage Built	.751**	.704**	.683**	.660**	.661**	.726**	.788**
Safeguard historical places	.605**	.682**	.710**	.698**	.696**	.763**	.740**
Property Value	.707**	.625**	.579**	.568**	.491**	.592**	.694**
Overall Practices of Nationalism	.761**	.767**	.763**	.753**	.741**	.818**	.847**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table shows the result of the test of correlation among the variables of perceived level of practices of nationalism and level of heritage conservation. The R-values are verbally interpreted ranging from the strong

association (value of $r=+.40$ to $+6.0$) to very strong \pm association ($r=+.8$ to $+1.0$). They are being tested at $p<.05$ significant level.

As to perception of respondents on level of heritage conservation in terms of community participation, tourism development, historical values, aesthetic values, and scientific values shows a significant relationship with the level of nationalism as to preservation, restoration, heritage built, safeguarding historical places and property value.

Respondents' community participation recognize that heritage encourages a variety of cultural activities from the local population has significant relationship with preservation that understand the benefits of tourism and heritage in the community. Moreover, respondents know that local people should be consulted when tourism and heritage conservation policies are being made by supporting community efforts for appropriate information on restoration. Also, their willingness to attend the local government programs on heritage conservation to increase awareness by appreciate tangible heritage such as movable, immovable and heritage sites. Furthermore, respondents want to promote community-based tourism initiatives and heritage conservation activities through showing of patriotism towards built heritage, historical landmarks, etc.

The effectiveness of the conservation program depends on the participation and involvement of the locals, which should be promoted. In addition, community involvement is necessary for historical conservation to be sustainable (Butowski, 2016).

Tourism development skills of the respondents understand the concept of sustainable tourism, provide regular upkeep for historic area believing that well-managed attractions such as your maintained in their natural state, are important to attract tourism, advocate for maintaining and expanding historical ideas on restoration to provide knowledge. Promoting tourism and encouraging the community to participate should be involved in the promotion of heritage in the community. Respondents can see that the people in the community protect local heritage and tourism by safeguarding plans and documents should be drawn up, once all the necessary advance scientific studies have been carried out, by multidisciplinary teams involved in the protection and enhancement of historic areas. Locals can benefit from developing a sustainable tourism framework and be proud of their identity and nationality.

Conclusion

Among the 200 pre-service teachers, 37 students or 18.4 percent are English majors, 38 students or 18.90 percent are Filipino majors, 12 students or 6.50 percent are General Education majors, 9 students or 4.50 percent are MAPEH majors, 28 students or 13.90 percent are Mathematics majors, 31 students or 15.40 percent are Science majors, 44 students or 21.90 percent are Social Studies majors, while 1 student or 0.50 percent, is TLE major. Under the level of nationalism, property value obtained the highest mean of 3.71. Students strongly agreed that they are proud on their identity and nationality. Community participation received the highest mean of 3.56 in terms of level of heritage conservation. Students strongly agreed the benefits of tourism and heritage in the community. Aesthetic had the highest mean of 3.45 in terms of level of values on heritage conservation. Students agreed the importance of creativity in creating design or technical advancement. The results of the test of the relationship between nationalism and heritage conservation among pre-service teachers indicate that there is a significant positive relationship between the respondents' levels of nationalism and level of heritage conservation. Since the obtained R-values are less than the critical R-value, the study concluded that there is sufficient evidence at the 0.01 level of significance to reject the null hypothesis and establish that respondents' nationalism is significantly associated to heritage conservation. This suggests that as students' nationalism grows, also their awareness to heritage conservation increases. Based on the findings, it is concluded that: There is a significant relationship between nationalism and heritage conservation, thus, the null hypothesis of the study was not sustained.

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are offered:

The College of Teacher Education may provide opportunities among the pre-service teachers to strengthen their nationalism and participation in heritage conservation as part of the curriculum contents of the subject in Social Sciences. Pre-service teachers may be encouraged to inculcate the value of heritage in their students through learning activities in face-to-face, blended learning, modular distance learning or online media platforms in their teaching the subject in social science. Pre-service teachers may be encouraged to participate on different activities related to heritage conservation that encourage positive relationships and nationalism.

Acknowledgement/Any declaration

The researchers would like to express their appreciation and gratitude to everyone who contributed to the study's success, to the people who inspired and motivated them to pursue this study, as well as for the valuable guidance and professional support in overcoming the challenges and difficulties encountered while conducting this research.

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CONCLUSIONS

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